

Landslide Problem in Bangladesh: a review with Special focus on Chittagong Region

Maksudur Rahman Asif & Muhammad Sher Mahmud

Abstract:

This article makes an effort to discuss several aspects of the assessment risk, effects and mitigation of landslides in Bangladesh. A considerable number of research works have been done in recent years regarding this topic and this article presents a summary review of some of the published works. Globally Bangladesh is recognized as one of the most vulnerable countries to natural calamities. Along with cyclones and floods; two most discussed and disastrous hazards of the country, landslides have caused the death of nearly 235 people in various informal settlements of Chittagong city and its adjacent urban centers since 1997. Ineffective hill management policy at the national level and weak enforcement by the local authorities has created space for growing many informal settlements along landslide prone hill slopes and foothills in Chittagong city. Based on the review of literature and published case records, it is recommended that the city of Chittagong should consider establishing a sustainable long-term landslide management plan. The practical use of this paper is that the future researcher can get a details geomorphological information of landslide which is very helpful for their research work.

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Introduction

Landslide is a general term for a wide variety of down slope movements of earth materials that result in the perceptible downward and outward movement of soil, rock, and vegetation under the influence of gravity. The materials may move by falling, toppling, sliding, spreading, or flowing. Some landslides are rapid, occurring in seconds, whereas others may take hours, weeks, or even longer to develop. Although the landslides are primarily associated with mountainous terrains, these can also occur in areas where an activity such as surface excavations for highways, buildings and open pit mines takes place (Anwar, 2007). A landslide is a type of "mass wasting." Mass wasting is down slope movement of soil and/or rock under the influence of gravity. A landslide is a movement of mass rock, debris, or earth down a slope. The failure of the slope happens when gravity exceeds the strength of the earth materials (Brammer, 1996).

METHODOLOGY

The methodologies used in the selected study area were characteristically involved data collection, data processing and field checking. A number of primary and secondary data were collected from various sources. These included base map from Chittagong Development Authority (CDA) and satellite image of LANDSET 7. A study area field survey was supported out in landslides vulnerable area. The experience, observations, analysis of the data and information logical interpretation in a systematic manner largely received to achieve the goal. Existing planning interventions (Master plan and DAP), journals, published and unpublished books, articles, newsletter by GOs (CDA, CCC, and LGED) and some Non-government Organizations newsletter were also used literature review. The paper present on land cover changing profile and hill cutting scenarios of Chittagong city corporation area and how do hill cutting sequenced landslide.

Study Area

Chittagong city is situated within 22°-14' and 22°24'30'' N Latitude and between 91°46' and 91°53' E Longitude and on the right bank of the river Karnaphuli. It is considered highly vulnerable areas where there are some human lives lost every year.

Selection of the study area

Landslide is a regular geologic hazard in Bangladesh, especially in Chittagong city. Especially, some areas of the city locally called Motijharna, Baizid Bostami, Kushumbag residential area, Batali Hill and Lebubagan are vulnerable to landslide. Among these areas, Batali hill and Motijharna are most densely populated and landslide prone area. For this reason, Batali hill and Motijharna have been selected for this study (Fig. 1).

Fig. Map of Bangladesh showing Chittagong district, with an embedded Google Earth image of the study area

Objectives of This Research

The aim of this research is to find out the causes of land slide and the vulnerable areas. The specific objectives of this research are in the following:

- a) To organize and evaluate the research publication regarding landslide in Chittagong region
- b) To find out the causes and possible solutions of landslide in the area
- c) To recommend new research scopes, if possible.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Physiographic Features of Bangladesh Hills

Bangladesh has a varied physical geography and her area is characterized by two distinctive features: a broad deltaic plain and a small hilly region crossed by swiftly flowing rivers. Major portion of the total landmass is made up of fertile alluvial lowland which is part of the larger Plain of Bengal. Although altitudes up to 105 meters above sea level occur in the northern part of the plain, most elevations are less than 10 meters above sea level; elevations decrease in the coastal south, where the terrain is generally at sea level. The only exception to Bangladesh's low elevations is the small hilly region. 18% land of Bangladesh can be identified as terrace and hilly area. Pleistocene terrace has covered 10% and eastern and north-eastern tertiary hill are of only 8% of the country (Islam & Uddin, 2002). Physiographically, hilly Regions can be divided into the following three sub-regions:

1. Chittagong and Chittagong Hill Tract in the southeast
2. Hill Ranges of Northeastern Sylhet
3. Hill along the narrow northern strip of Sylhet and Mymensingh in the north and Northwest

Chittagong Hills constitute the only significant hill system in the country and, in effect, are the western fringe of the north-south mountain ranges of Burma and eastern India. The Chittagong Hills rise steeply to narrow ridge lines, generally no wider than 36 meters, with Altitudes from 600 to 900 meters above sea level. At 1,052 meters altitude, the highest elevation in Bangladesh is found at Mowdok Mual, in the southeastern part of the hills. Fertile valleys lay between the hill lines, which generally run north-south. West of the Chittagong Hills is a broad plain, cut by rivers draining into the Bay of Bengal that rises to a final chain of low coastal hills, mostly below 200 meters, that attain a maximum elevation of 350 meters. West of these hills is a narrow, wet coastal plain located between the cities of Chittagong in the north and Cox's Bazar in the south (Anwar, 2007). Hills of Bangladesh have been uplifted and folded into a series of pitching anticlines and synclines. The higher hill ranges in the Chittagong Hill Tracts, Chittagong and Sylhet regions regarded as late Oligocene to mid-Miocene in age. Lower hills are mainly underlain by little-consolidated sands and shales of the Dupi Tila formation, which may be from late-Miocene age (Brammer, 1996). These hills are mainly composed by unconsolidated or little-consolidated beds of sandstones, siltstones and shales, together with minor beds of limestone and conglomerates. Nature of parent materials strongly determines the texture of the soils. Shale results heavy silt loam or silty clay loam subsoil. Soils developed on sandstone have dominant textural class of sandy loams with occasional loamy sand or loam texture. Soils subject to erosion have topsoil with less clay content. The steepness of the landscape determines the depth of the soil. Soils are in general shallow in depth. Soils developed at steep or very steep slopes of the hilly regions are susceptible to erosion (including landslips on some soils). Washout materials are deposited at the foot of the hills (FAO, 1988).

Fig: 1 Physiographic Features of Bangladesh

Source: Sarker and Rashid, 2013

Landslide Risk in Hilly Region of Bangladesh

Geologists, engineers, and other professionals often rely on unique and slightly differing definitions of landslides. This diversity in definitions reflects the complex nature of the many disciplines associated with this disaster. Landslide is a general term used to describe the down slope movement of soil, rock, and organic materials under the effects of gravity and also the landform that results from such movement. It is a natural phenomenon and accelerated by human interventions. Landslide is one of the neglected disasters in Bangladesh as much as these took place in isolated and dispersed locations and do not create big headlines as earthquake, flood or cyclone does. The cumulative effects of landslides, however, in terms of lives, properties and infrastructure have been quiet substantial. There have been instances when many settlements in hilly slopes have gone into complete oblivion and many rural and urban settlements have been very severely affected due to landslides.

Bangladesh is affected by landslides due to variety of factors; both natural and manmade. Amongst the natural factors, geology as well as hydro-meteorology has played their parts. Earthquakes with even lesser magnitude have triggered massive movement in the hilly slopes. Incessant rainfall has been a more common factor for causing landslides. Even cyclonic storms and resulting precipitation resulted landslides in the hills, as cyclone AILA had demonstrated. The climate change and its impact on glacial melts and changing rainfall pattern have the potentiality of increasing both the frequency and intensity of landslides. Large scale deforestation has definitely increased the incidence of landslides just as unplanned settlements intensified the impact of such disaster.

Table 1: Landslide susceptibility to different soil erosion in the hilly areas of Bangladesh

Area	Moderate susceptibility	High Susceptibility	Very high susceptibility	Total
Chittagong Hill Tracts	350	1,814	10,765	12,929
Chittagong & Cox's Bazar	414	949	954	2,317
Greater Sylhet District	-	35	102	137
Others (comilla, Netrokona, Jamalpur)	-	35	105	137
Total	925(5%)	3,260(20%)	12,785(75%)	16,970(100%)

Source: Sarker and Rashid, 2013; Khan, 2008

Causes of Landslide in Bangladesh

Landslide is occurred due to both internal and external forces. Slope failure and mass wasting occurs when acting gravitational force exceeds its resisting force on a slope. Slopes stability is maintained by slope material's strength and cohesion and the amount of internal friction between materials. It is also known as shear strength of slope. Landslide occurs when the stability of a slope changes from a stable to an unstable condition. A change in the stability can be caused by a number of factors, acting together or alone. There are two primary causes associated with major landslides in Bangladesh; natural causes and human induced causes. Sometimes, landslides are caused, or made worse, by a combination of the two factors. Natural causes are the major mechanism for landslides. A single reason or a combination of different natural reasons may cause this disaster. Effects of these causes varied widely and depend on steepness of slope, morphology or shape of the terrain, soil properties, and underlying geology etc. Human induced causes such as unplanned settlement in the risky zone, modern agricultural practice without considering soil type, cutting hill for roads and other constructions without considering proper slope etc. increase the intensity of the impact of landslide (Khan, 1991)

Natural Causes:

Slope saturation by water is the primary cause of the landslide. Saturation can be occurred due to intense rainfall, changes in ground-water levels and surface water level changes along coastlines, earth dams and in the banks of lakes, reservoirs, canals and rivers (Highland & Bodrowsky, 2008). Precipitation and run-off are closely related to the sudden inundation of

hill slope and landslide. Flooding may cause landslides by undercutting banks of streams and rivers and by saturation of slopes by surface water (overland flow). Conversely, landslides also can cause flooding when sliding rock and debris block stream channels and other waterways, allowing large volumes of water to back up behind such dams. Previous geological events or modern irrigation practice may cause losing soil particles and ease the saturation process. Deforestation helps in removal of topsoil from the surface of the hill. Few major natural causes of landslide are: rainfall, earthquake, soil Composition, gravity.

Human Interventions

Expanding population in the landslide prone area due to migration are the primary means by which humans are contributing to the landslide disasters. The new settlement creates disturbance to the natural drainage system and destabilize the slopes. Unsustainable and unplanned use of land for industrial purpose and irrigation practice by the migrated people is also reducing stability of the soil for containing moisture and losing bondage of top soil. Landslide related human induced factors are: hill cutting, informal settlement, deforestation and afforestation, modern irrigation practice, inappropriate drainage system

Figure 2: Causes of landslide

Source: Rahman, 2013

Landslide Vulnerability in Chittagong

In a landslide or rock falls, movements of the materials depend on the slope is caused by the slope instability, commonly observed in Chittagong and its adjacent areas of Bangladesh. Several geological, morphological, and human induced changes cause these slope instabilities. Chittagong hills are the part of tertiary hills. The geological structure and soils are weak of these hills and also have steep slopes which increase the risk of landslide. Risk is higher where settlement exists on the foothills and poor people live within the areas. Over the last few decades landslides have become an increasingly serious hazard, with much of the city's expansion a result of hill cutting for unplanned urban development. Since 1997, 15 landslides have killed nearly 400 people in the city and adjacent small urban centers. For example, the landslide disaster in June 2007 that was triggered by intense rainfall killed 128 people and affected 2,072 families in five informal settlements (Khan, 2008). After the massive landslide

of 2007, a technical committee has been created consisted of government agencies, Chittagong City Corporation (CCC), Chittagong Development Authority (CDA), researchers, engineers and NGO workers for identifying priorities for action, land use vulnerability assessment and zoning. That committee divided the city into 3 (three) zones considering risking issues of landslide. After the disastrous incidence of the year 2007, national and local level organizations came to know about the threat and severity of the apparently neglected natural hazard, landslide. Ministry of Food and Disaster Management included landslide as a national level natural disaster. Death toll went up in landslide incidences which took place later. In the year 2010, a workshop was held by SAARC at Bhutan titled "Landslide Risk Management in South Asia". (Mahmood & Khan, 2010) presented a paper on that workshop considering the landslide of 2007 as a case study. In that, they conducted GPS (Global Positioning System) survey to prepare a landslide prone zoning map which was adopted by the disaster management committee later. (Mahmood & Khan, 2010) divided Chittagong city in to three different zones according to vulnerability of landslides:

- High Risk Areas: Lebugagan area, Baizid Bostami area, Kushumbag residential area, Batali Hill area, Motijharna area
- Moderate Risk Area: Foy's Lake Area, Khulshi area
- Low Vulnerable areas: Nasirabad area, Goalpara Slum

Figure 3: Post-landslide conditions in Motijharna Area

Source: The Daily Star

Effects of Landslides

Landslides are a major catastrophe the world as it is widespread and significant impact, including Bangladesh. The effect of catastrophic landslides is dangerous to humans and to other living things. For example, the slope of the saturated with water to form debris flows or mud flows. Concentrated mixture of rock and mud may destroy the trees, houses, death of

human, blocking the road network & drain fill up.

Economic Decline

Landslides are certainly cause damage to property. This brings losses to the economy of a country. On an average, these landslides caused loss of Tk.1-2 million in Bangladesh each year.

Damage to Infrastructure

Landslides can lead to damage to property resulting from the force flow or mud. Infrastructure land such as buildings, roads, places of leisure and so on can be destroyed by the landslide occurred. Landslide in June 2007 and in June 2011 affected road communication system, property damage and destruction of homes.

Loss of Life

Loss of life is a dangerous effect upon the occurrence of a landslide and it is difficult to avoid. Many lives will be lost upon the occurrence of landslides. 150 people were killed and many injured as a result of the landslide in Chittagong in June 2007 and in June 2011.

Changes in the Surface Landscape

Landslide causes significant changes in the landscape of the earth's surface. Pile of soil and mud from the landslide activity caused the high ground may be flat and settling sediment can become thick very quickly. Consequently dam of rivers or lakes become more shallow to hold a lot of water. Water level becomes higher and the ground becomes waterlogged areas.

Mitigation of Landslide

Landslide may be mitigated by Structural and Non Structural Measures.

Drainage Corrections

The most important triggering mechanism for mass movements is the water infiltrating into the overburden during heavy rains and consequent increase in pore pressure within the overburden. Hence the natural way of preventing this situation is by reducing infiltration and allowing excess water to move down without hindrance. As such, the first and foremost mitigation measure is drainage correction. This involves maintenance of natural drainage channels both micro and macro in vulnerable slopes.

Proper land use measures

Adopt effective land-use regulations and building codes based on scientific research. Through land-use planning, discourage new construction or development in identified hazard areas without first implementing appropriate remedial measures.

Structural measures

Adopt remedial techniques (i.e., buttresses, shear keys, sub-drains, soil reinforcement, retaining walls, etc.) of existing landslides that are in close proximity to public structures.

Afforestation

The afforestation programme should be properly planned so the little slope modification is done in the process. Bounding of any sort using boulders etc. has to be avoided. The selection of suitable plant species should be such that can with stand the existing stress conditions of the terrain.

Awareness generation

Educate the public about signs that a landslide is imminent so that personal safety measures may be taken.

Some of these signs include:

- (i) Springs, seeps, or saturated ground in areas that have not typically been wet before.
- (ii) New cracks or unusual bulges in the ground, street pavements or sidewalks.

- (iii) Soil moving away from foundations, and ancillary structures such as decks and patios tilting and/or moving relative to the house.
- (iv) Sticking doors and windows, and visible open spaces.
- (v) Broken water lines and other underground utilities.
- (vi) Leaning telephone poles, trees, retaining walls or fences.
- (vii) Sunken or dropped-down road beds.
- (viii) Rapid increase in a stream or creek water levels, possibly accompanied by increased turbidity (soil content).
- (ix) Sudden decrease in creek water levels even though rain is still falling or just recently stopped.

Financial Mechanisms

Support the establishment of landslide insurance

Legal and Policy

Legislation to direct a governmental or private program to reduce landslide losses should be strengthened.

Preparedness for Mitigating Landslide Hazard

Before the Landslide

Develop a Family Disaster Plan:

Develop landslide-specific planning. Learn about landslide risk in your area. Contact local officials or departments of natural resources, and university departments of geology. Landslides occur where they have before, and in identifiable hazard locations. Ask for information on landslides in your area, specific information on areas vulnerable to landslides, and request a professional referral for a very detailed site analysis of your property, and corrective measures you can take, if necessary. If you are at risk from landslides: Develop an evacuation plan. You should know where to go if you have to leave. Trying to make plans at the last minute can be upsetting and create confusion. Discuss landslides and debris flow with your family. Everyone should know what to do in case all family members are not together. Discussing disaster ahead of time helps reduce fear and lets everyone know how to respond during a landslide or debris flow.

During a Landslide

Stay alert and awake. Many debris-flow fatalities occur when people are sleeping. Listen to early warning of intense rainfall. Be aware that intense, short bursts of rain may be particularly dangerous, especially after longer periods of heavy rainfall and damp weather. If you are in areas susceptible to landslides and debris flows, consider leaving if it is safe to do so. Remember that driving during an intense storm can be hazardous. If you remain at home, move to a second story if possible. Staying out of the path of a landslide or debris flow saves lives. Listen for any unusual sounds that might indicate moving debris, such as trees cracking or boulders knocking together. A trickle of flowing or falling mud or debris may precede larger landslides. Moving debris can flow quickly and sometimes without warning. If you are near a stream or channel, be alert for any sudden increase or decrease in water flow and for a change from clear to muddy water. Such changes may indicate landslide activity upstream, so be prepared to move quickly. Don't delay! Save yourself, not your belongings. Especially alert when driving. Embankments along roadsides are particularly susceptible to landslides.

Watch the road for collapsed pavement, mud, fallen rocks, and other indications of possible debris flows.

After the Landslide

Stay away from the slide area. There may be danger of additional slides. Check for injured and trapped persons near the slide, without entering the direct slide area. Help a neighbor who may require special assistance - infants, elderly people, and people with disabilities. Elderly people and people with disabilities may require additional assistance. People who care for them or who have large families may need additional assistance in emergency situations. Listen to local radio or television stations for the latest emergency information. Watch for flooding, which may occur after a landslide or debris flow. Floods sometimes follow landslides and debris flows because they may both be started by the same event. Look for and report broken utility lines to appropriate authorities. Reporting potential hazards will get the utilities turned off as quickly as possible, preventing further hazard and injury. Check the building foundation, chimney, and surrounding land for damage. Damage to foundations, chimneys, or surrounding land may help you assess the safety of the area. Replant damaged ground as soon as possible since erosion caused by loss of ground cover can lead to flash flooding. Seek the advice of a geotechnical expert for evaluating landslide hazards or designing corrective techniques to reduce landslide risk. A professional will be able to advise you of the best ways to prevent or reduce landslide risk, without creating further hazard.

Recommendation

1. Planning Measure

Every year during the monsoon, occurrence of landslide is common in Chittagong City, Bangladesh. These landslides cause closure to roads, affect settlements and worse cause casualties. The potential economic loss and loss of life could escalate if the causes of landslides of Chittagong are not identified and addressed properly by all parties, stake holders especially by the government, planners, contractors, engineers and developers directly or indirectly involved in the development of buildings and roads over the hilly terrain. The selection of appropriate mitigation measure should be based on assessment of risk, uncertainty, possible consequences, constructability, environmental impacts and costs. A final enhancement approach usually consists of a creative combination of several methods. Environmental constraints and requirements can influence the selection and overall design of mitigation measures.

2. Considerations

Motijharna- Batali Hill informal settlement is a populous hill slope & foot hill settlement, severely affected by landslides of 2007, 2011, 2012. Landslide mitigation works are needed to be conducted in order to stop or reduce the landslide movement so that the resulting damages can be minimized. With a clear understanding of the causes and mechanics of the landslide of the study area, the landslide control works can be implemented. For this a number of issues are considered.

2.1 Informal Settlers

Over the last few years, low income people occupied unused railway owned hills illegally and built Motijharna- Batali Hill informal settlement in Chittagong City. It is one of the dense informal settlements of Chittagong city. It is the biggest amongst all the informal settlements and situated at the center of the city. The informal settlers mainly work at nearby places and live here in cheap rate. Though the area was severely damaged by landslide of 2007 and

2012, none of the inhabitants want to leave this place. Their livelihood is deeply rooted with this location and feels threatened whenever government wanted to relocate them. While designing the mitigation measure this issue has been seriously considered and the proposal prepared for immediate risk reduction needs least eviction and relocation. Motijharna informal settlement is oldest of all the informal settlement and is badly reputed to be the shelter home of anti-social activists. Introvert nature of the settlement induces this type of activity more. Providing a community space and making the space open to all sorts of people may reduce this type of activities. Law makers and protectors may ensure the security of the inhabitants and also the outsider beneficiaries.

2.2 Inadequate Basic Facilities

As informal settlements are considered 'illegal', populations who live in these settlements often have no official addresses and are commonly denied basic rights and entitlements, including the right to access water, sanitation, healthcare services, and education. During the study, it is found that neither Batali Hill nor Motijharna informal settlements have access to these basic services. Even after the disastrous event of 2007, none of the settlements have been included in the "Detail Area Plan".

2.3 Degraded Environment

Batali hill and Motirjharna used to be a place of scenic beauty and once one of the major sources of water before piped water was introduced in Chittagong city. Because of unplanned growth of the informal settlement and unsustainable land use pattern both of the places degraded environmentally.

Conclusion

Landslide is a curse for modern life. Its effects are very dangerous. Man's activity is the prime cause of Landslide. Man's cutting hill unwisely and alter the natural slope of hill for various purposes. Poor people and some land greedy rich person make their house in hill slope and foothills. To reduce the negative effects of land we should take necessary steps like stop hill cutting, build safety wall and not build our residence in hill slope. Then we save our life and wealth from the grasp of landslide effect. Nature has favored Chittagong city, like the entire district, with many natural springs. The sources of most of these springs are to be found in the hill ranges. The water from these springs is used for irrigation purposes as well as to supply drinking water. In the city proper there are a number of springs, which are bounded by concrete walls by the Municipal authorities and supply drinking water.

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